

Radial Basis Functions for Stochastic Metamodels Tailored to Aeroacoustic Applications

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ABSTRACT

The paper presents a preliminary investigation on the applicability of stochastic Radial Basis Functions (RBF) in the development of dynamically adaptive meta-models for aeroacoustic applications. The analysis focuses on the influence of the RBF kernel and the chosen stochastic parameters on the modelling of target functions of interest in the aeroacoustics of aircraft. The rationale underlying the research is related to the key role that aeroacoustics plays in the establishment of the commercial aviation scenario foreseen for the next three decades. Indeed, the sustainable development for the airborne transportation system is strongly constrained by community noise, which, nowadays, limits the increase of the capacity of the existing airports and prevents the building of new ones. In such a situation, the design of the next generation of aircraft must take into account the impact of noise on the population since the early conceptual phase of the design. This causes a substantial increase of the required computational resources, especially for unconventional, breakthrough concepts for which simple semi-empirical models are not available and the only viable strategy is computational aeroacoustics. The availability of reliable meta-models can give a significant contribution in two ways: *i*) in a process of multiobjective, multidisciplinary design optimization a dynamic adaptive stochastic meta-model can reduce significantly the calls to the computationally expansive tools and enhance the effectiveness of the design space exploration; *ii*) the versatility and applicability range of end-user tools for the estimate community noise impact can be greatly improved by fast yet accurate models of the noise signature of novel concepts. Two target functions are analysed here: the total acoustic field induced by a point source co-moving with a scattering profile, and the shielding factor along a line of observation points below the scatterer. The performance of RBF meta-models based on tailored kernels is compared to the most commonly used kernels in terms of accuracy and convergence rate. The effectiveness of the dynamic meta-model update based on uncertainty quantification is assessed for different choices of the stochastic parameter.

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1 Introduction

The sustainable development of the airborne transportation system is currently one of the major commitments of the aeronautical engineering community to guarantee the satisfaction of the growing market demand in a context where most of the existing airports are close to the operational saturation. The enhancement of the environmental friendliness of commercial aircraft is thus paramount. On the other hand, nowadays noise signature and gas emissions cannot be easily further reduced without the introduction of breakthrough technologies and concepts, due to the technological saturation of the conventional architectures. Hence, the analysis of the environmental signature of the novel configurations must be taken into account since the early conceptual phase of the design. The unconventionality of the new concepts makes inapplicable the existing semi-empirical and analytical models, thus imposing the inclusion of computationally expensive numerical simulations in the conceptual design frameworks, increasing the computational burden of the entire process by order of magnitudes. In addition, the need to rely on direct numerical methods introduces in the conceptual optimization uncertainties related to the convergence of the simulations under significant variations of the design point (e.g., adaptation of the computational grid to geometry variations or convergence of numerical integration for varying operation conditions). For these reasons, it is of primary importance the identification of procedures to concentrate the use of the available resources in the exploration of the most relevant areas of the design domain, optimizing the extraction of information from the simulations. Furthermore, the forthcoming advent of breakthrough concepts induces an additional issue related to the impact on the population of the noise produced by the civil aviation operations. Indeed, the human response to noise depends strongly and in an extremely complex way on the acoustic landscape produced by the entire set of operations at a specific airport, rather than on the peculiarities of the emission of a specific aircraft. The estimate of the noise maps on the ground must be done taking into account all the operations in the time slot of interest, thus imposing the use of simple prediction models, typically based on the regression of existing data. The lack of such data for innovative concepts makes the evaluation of their impact on the noise mapping extremely time consuming, if not even impossible.

The development of dynamic meta-models is one of the most promising strategies to answer to the above issues in an effective fashion. In a context of multidisciplinary design optimization (MDO), a dynamically evolving meta-model can help significantly in reducing the number of calls to the expensive simulation models (in the present context, typically CFD and CAA) and avoid the wasting of resources in irrelevant areas of the design space. In the development of noise impact management and prediction tools, efficient meta-models can provide an estimate of the effect of unconventional concepts and procedures at a reasonable computational cost.

Here, we analyse the potential of dynamically adaptive meta-modelling techniques based on the use of stochastic Radial Basis Functions (RBF) in aeroacoustic applications. Specifically, we investigate on the influence of the RBF kernel in the accurate and efficient reproduction of a target response. Indeed, RBF-based meta-models can be implemented and integrated in existing frameworks in a very simple way, being, at the same time, extremely versatile in the choice of the kernel suited to the application at hand. This is particularly helpful in aeroacoustic application, where the target response can exhibit a complex periodic pattern due to the combined effect of scattering, reflection and convection.

Section 2 describes the structure of a generic meta-model based on stochastic RBF and lists a set of kernels suitable for aeroacoustic applications. The capability of the selected kernels in the static reproduction of benchmark response is presented in Section 3, whereas Section 4 describes the dynamically adapting algorithm. Finally, the results of numerical simulations in terms of convergence rate of different basis-functions applied to the adaptive technique are presented in Section 5. In the same section, some additional results of aeroacoustic application are addressed,

analysing the behaviour on a bi-dimensional design space. In Section 6, all the conclusions will be gathered.

2 Meta-models based on stochastic RBF

The use of RBF for the reproduction of a dataset is a standard, well established interpolation technique [1, 2]. Let's consider a target response $f(\boldsymbol{\xi})$, solution of a certain problem governed by an arbitrarily complex set of PDEs for $\boldsymbol{\xi} \in \mathcal{D}$, where \mathcal{D} is the design domain of interest. Also assume that an analytical form of f is not available, and its value can be obtained only numerically through expensive computational tools for specified values of the design variable $\boldsymbol{\xi}$. Given a training set (TS) of couples $(\boldsymbol{\xi}_i, f(\boldsymbol{\xi}_i))$ for $i = 1, N_T$, a simple interpolation of the data using RBF has the form

$$\check{f}(\boldsymbol{\xi}) = \sum_{j=1}^{N_T} w_j \varphi(|\boldsymbol{\xi} - \boldsymbol{\xi}_j|) \quad (1)$$

with weights w_j obtained by imposing the values at the TS points by solving $\mathbf{w} = \mathbf{A}^{-1} \mathbf{f}$ with $A_{ij} = \varphi(|\boldsymbol{\xi}_i - \boldsymbol{\xi}_j|)$ and $f_j = f(\boldsymbol{\xi}_j)$. The accuracy of the interpolating function $\check{f}(\boldsymbol{\xi})$ for $\boldsymbol{\xi} \notin TS$ depends on the characteristics of the RBF kernel $\varphi(|\boldsymbol{\xi} - \boldsymbol{\xi}_j|) = \varphi(r)$ and, of course, on the properties of the TS . The third column of Table 1 lists some possible form of the RBF kernel. Among the large variety existing in the literature, the analysis is here limited to only a few, having properties of some relevance in the present context. A first classification can be made in term of properties of the function support: the first three are not compactly supported, whereas the last two are identically zero for $r \geq r_0$. Another distinction concerns the possibility of the kernel to have an oscillatory behaviour or not. This properties are of primary importance in the aeroacoustic context, where, as already pointed out, the target response is typically a complex wavy field. However, the objective of the present work is not the simple interpolation of the data using Eq. 1, but rather the development of an adaptive meta-model capable to quantify the information about the unknown response $f(\boldsymbol{\xi})$ contained in the available TS . To this aim, the RBF meta-model is reinterpreted in a statistical fashion introducing a stochastic variation of one of the parameters of the RBF kernel. The stochastic parameters used in the present preliminary analysis are listed in the fifth column of the table. The parameter chosen for the polynomial spline is the polynomial degree a , following Volpi *et al.* [3], where the effectiveness of the choice is demonstrated for a rich set of benchmark functions and a CFD problem for naval applications. The choice of the most relevant parameter for the remaining kernels is one of the key aspects of the present work, and stems from considerations about the nature of the target response. As already mentioned, the acoustic field in aeroacoustic applications is typically characterised by a complex spatial structure strongly influenced by the effects of convection, scattering of moving obstacles and reflection from surfaces with various geometry and impedance. The local wavelength "observed" at the monitoring points is thus varying from point to point in a very articulated way. The idea underlying the present work is to use RBF with an oscillatory kernel with the wave number k as stochastic parameter. The stochastic meta-model is thus defined as the expected value of the deterministic one for the stochastic parameter α subject to a uniform probability density function

$$\hat{f}(\boldsymbol{\xi}) = EV \left[\sum_{j=1}^{N_T} w_j \varphi(|\boldsymbol{\xi} - \boldsymbol{\xi}_j|, \alpha) \right], \quad \alpha \sim Unif [\alpha_{min}, \alpha_{max}] \quad (2)$$

The meta-model response is then associated to a local uncertainty $U(\boldsymbol{\xi})$ defined as the 95% confidence band of $\hat{f}(\boldsymbol{\xi})$, i.e. $U(\boldsymbol{\xi}) = CDF^{-1}(\boldsymbol{\xi}, 0.975) - CDF^{-1}(\boldsymbol{\xi}, 0.025)$, where $CDF(\boldsymbol{\xi}, y)$ is the

local value of the cumulative density function and its inverse is the quantile $Q(y)$. An appropriate choice of the stochastic parameter allows the conjecture that higher values of U correspond to a local lack of knowledge about the target response dynamics.

Table 1: RBF kernels used in the present analysis

support	type	$\varphi(r)$	plot	candidate stochastic parameters
Non compact	Polynomial spline	r^a		polynomials degree a
	Gauss-Laguerre	$e^{-\frac{r^2}{(r_0/3)^2}} \left(\frac{3}{2} - r^2\right)$		Gaussian width r_0
	Gaussian wave packet	$e^{-\frac{r^2}{(r_0/3)^2}} \cos(kr)$		Gaussian width r_0 Wave number k
Compact	Truncated Bessel	$\max\left(1 - \frac{ r }{r_0}, 0\right) J_0(kr)$		Truncation point r_0 Wave number k
	Cosine wave packet	$\frac{1}{2}\Pi\left(\frac{r}{2r_0}\right) \left[1 - \cos\left(\frac{\pi r}{r_0}\right)\right] \cos(kr)$		Truncation point r_0 Wave number k

3 Benchmark problem

The present section is dedicated to the application of Eq. 2 to a very simple benchmark: the pressure generated by an isotropic point source in $\mathbf{x}_s \equiv (0,0)$ moving at $M_s = 0.3$, measured along a line of microphones at $y = 6$. Despite its simplicity, the target response, depicted in Fig.1, exhibits some of the features that make aeroacoustic meta-modelling a challenging problem. The target function exhibits a varying local wave length as a consequence of the source motion. The statistics of the meta-model is calculated using the Monte Carlo method. Figure 2 shows the response of the surrogate models obtained by the static application of Eq. 2 to the simple 1D benchmark. The target response (black line in the graphs) is the pressure signal produced by a point source moving at $M_s = 0.3$. The TS is made of 15 uniformly spaced points. The only variable of the surrogate model is the position of the monitoring points. The subfigures show the results obtained by applying Eq. 2 to the TS with the kernels and the stochastic parameters listed in Table 1. The surrogate response is represented by the dashed red line, with the uncertainty region in pale yellow. Figure 2(a) depicts the response obtained with the polynomial kernel with the degree as stochastic parameter uniformly distributed in the range $[1, 3]$. This kernel is clearly able to reproduce in a satisfactory way the low-wavelength region of the training domain, but not the one where the Doppler shift is > 0 . In addition, the uncertainty of the surrogate model is very low in all the TS intervals. In the present context, the latter feature should be considered as a limitation. Indeed, the surrogate model uncertainty is the driving factor of the dynamic update of the MM (see Section 4) that allows for the automatic detection of the domain regions where the information about the target response is too poor. In this respect, it is worth emphasising one more time that a dynamically adaptive meta-modelling technique is not simply about the accurate

reproduction of data, but rather aims at capturing the “dynamics” underlying the data set, and identifying where additional knowledge is needed. From this point of view, the surrogate responses produced by the other kernels reveal to be much more promising. In all cases, two main features can be observed. First, all the kernels “attempt” to mimic the oscillatory behaviour of the target response, showing their capability to recognise the periodic nature of the underlying dynamics. In addition, the uncertainty associated to the stochastic variation of the parameters is higher in the regions where the surrogate response is less accurate, thus confirming that the selected stochastic parameters can effectively identify the region where additional information is needed. In the next Section, these features will be used to develop the dynamic adaptive algorithm.

Figure 1: Benchmark target response: pressure generated by an isotropic point source in $\mathbf{x}_s \equiv (0, 0)$ moving at $M_s = 0.3$, measured along a line of microphones at $y = 6$

Figure 2: Static reproduction of the benchmark field.

4 Dynamic adaptive meta-modelling

The meta-model uncertainty associated to the stochastic variation of the parameters listed in Table 1 can be used to estimate the region of the domain where the knowledge about the dynamics of the target response needs to be improved. An appropriate selection of the stochastic parameter can link directly the local statistical dispersion of the meta-model response to the local meta-model accuracy. It is important to notice that this procedure allows for an estimate of the local quality of the surrogate model without additional calls to the expensive simulation models.

The idea to apply oscillatory kernels to aeroacoustic applications comes from recent studies in which these basis-functions have been used to approximate numerical solutions for the 2D Helmholtz equation using a radial basis function-generated finite difference scheme (*RBF-FD*) on irregular domains [4, 5, 6, 7]. The RBFs are directly used as the basis to approximate the solutions by enforcing the governing equation and boundary conditions on collocation points. The power of this method for the solution of PDEs lies on the fact that RBFs are a meshless tool so as to do not require any prescribed structure (the weights depends only on the distance between the training set points) and they lead to a non-singularity of the interpolation matrix for scattered data in problems with dimensionality $d > 1$. Led by these facts, for the present study, this family of oscillatory kernels has been adopted to reproduce the dynamics of aeroacoustic engineering problems by interpolating few high-fidelity simulation data.

The flowchart of the dynamic adaptive algorithm is depicted in Fig.3. Starting from an initial *TS*, Eq. 2 is applied, and the local value of its uncertainty $U(\xi)$ is calculated. If the maximum value of the uncertainty is above a certain threshold ϵ , the *TS* is updated by adding a new sample ($\xi_{max}, f(\xi_{max})$), which is obtained exploring the variables domain by means of a genetic algorithm. The objective function for the search algorithm is the maximum uncertainty in prediction of the current surrogate model. This is the only step where the expensive model must be called. A constrain has been imposed on the minimum distance between points as to prevent ill-conditioning of the weight matrix in Eq.1. Once the point is collected, equation (2) is evaluated and the prediction on the test set points re-computed. For the polynomial kernel, satisfactory results have been so far obtained using a percentage of the function range as convergence value of U_{max} [8]. This procedure has been applied to the benchmark of Section 3 starting from an extremely coarse

Figure 3: Flowchart of the dynamic adaptive meta-model update

initial *TS* ($N_T = 5$). The results are shown in Section 5 for all the kernels presented in Table 1.

Particular attention should be paid at the sensitivity the kernels present to the stochastic variable in quantifying the meta-model uncertainty. Due to the different levels of U obtained by applying the proposed kernels and depending it strongly on the stochastic variables and their range, it was not possible to stop the adaptive scheme based on the meta-model uncertainty, as previously done. A different criterion based on the residual error between the true function and the prediction of the meta-model has been employed for the present study. Following [3], where the meta-model results are validated using the approach formulated in [9], the convergence of the

meta-model has been set at 5% residual of the uncertainty quantification error (E_{UQ})

$$E_{UQ} = \frac{|E_{EV}| + |E_{SD}| + E_{CDF}}{3} \quad (3)$$

where $|E_{EV}|$ is the error with respect to the expected value of the true function and the prediction, $|E_{SD}|$ is the error with respect to the standard deviation and E_{CDF} is the error with respect to the $CDF(EV) = P(X \leq EV)$. For the sake of completeness, the RMS error (E_{RMS}) computed at each iteration by the MM has been reported together with the E_{UQ}

$$E_{RMS}(\boldsymbol{\xi}) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N E(\boldsymbol{\xi}_i)^2} \quad \text{where} \quad E(\boldsymbol{\xi}) = \frac{f(\boldsymbol{\xi}) - \hat{f}(\boldsymbol{\xi})}{\max(f) - \min(f)} \quad (4)$$

The use of these metrics allows to better compare the kernels in terms of position and number of points which must be added to guarantee a certain level of accuracy of the final meta-model. In real-life applications, it would not be possible to base the convergence on the errors as the true function is unknown, but for the benchmark cases herein addressed this strategy helps to characterised the convergence trend of the proposed kernels and find out an approach to formulate a convergence criterion. For this reason, a detailed analysis on the uncertainty will be discussed for each kernel in the following section where the results are presented.

5 Results

In this Section, a comparison of the proposed kernels is reported. Special attention is paid to the convergence of these kernels and their sensitivity with regards to the stochastic variables used in the adaptive approach. In order to emphasize how the kernel is affected by the stochastic variable in terms of uncertainty, each figure shows the comparison of the surrogate model response (green line) with the target (black line), for the initial training set and after the convergence is reached. The uncertainty region related to the current iteration is shown in the figures with a violet area. An additional graph is reported for each case to show the evolution of the UQ error and the RMS error throughout iterations. It is worth mentioning that for all the analyses herein presented, the initial training set data has been sampled by using a uniform distribution in the design variables domain. The meta-model training samples are depicted in figures with blue dots. From these preliminary results, it can be observed that each kernel type exhibits a peculiar evolution which is not always consistent with the dynamics of the target response. It is worth noting that a maximum number of iterations has been set to 250 in the iterative scheme for the preliminary benchmark.

The polynomial kernel (Fig.4) converges to a solution of satisfactory quality with an evolution characterised by an always low uncertainty value. This means that the polynomial kernel can hardly recognise the periodic nature of the target, even though, for a sufficient number of points, the representation of the data is good (as can be expected by a polynomial interpolation).

A different behaviour can be observed in Fig 5 for the Gauss-Laguerre RBF, for which the uncertainty can be very high, but not necessarily where the surrogate response is less accurate. Again, this result can be ascribed to the lack of a periodic structure in the kernel definition. Even though the number of points added to reach the required convergence is lower than the polynomial case, the residual RMS error is higher, as it can be observed in Fig.5 top right. Moreover the residual uncertainty is localized in area where not always an additional number of points is required. The results herein reported are shown only for the stochastic variable range $r_0 \sim \text{Unif}[0.1, 0.5]$ which has been chosen from a preliminary analysis where several ranges have been tested.

From Fig.6 to 14, the results for three oscillatory kernels are presented. For all of these, two parameters have been tested as stochastic variable for the adaptive scheme: the kernel width r_0

Figure 4: Polynomial kernel behaviour to the stochastic variables $\alpha \sim \text{Unif}[1.0, 3.0]$.

Figure 5: Gauss-Laguerre behaviour to the stochastic variables $r_0 \sim \text{Unif}[0.1, 0.5]$.

and the wave number k for the Gaussian packet, the truncation factor r_0 and the wave number for Bessel and Cosine wave packet kernels. For the case of Gaussian wave packet, none of the case study converged, as it can be noted in Fig.6. The case of k stochastic variable has been tested for several values of r_0 : from very small kernel width ($r_0 = 0.01$), to see the local behaviour of the kernel function, up to $r_0 = 1.0$ to see its global performance. In Fig.6, on the top, the results for a compromise value ($r_0 = 0.5$) are shown. It has been noted that a local definition of the function provides a meta-model solution which is able to not diverge, even though it doesn't match the true function but is rather conditioned by its oscillating nature. Increasing the number of points, $r \rightarrow 0$ and the weight matrix in Eq.1 becomes ill-conditioned. To overcome this issue, regularization methods can be applied as proposed in [5]. In all the analysed cases with Gauss wave packet, the meta-model uncertainty increases continuously with the iterations degrading the meta-model prediction and the effectiveness of the optimization strategy.

In Fig.7-10, the results obtained using the Truncated Bessel kernel are shown. In the first case, the k parameter has been varied accordingly to the simulations which have been performed with $k = 4$ and $M = 0.3$ for different r_0 values. In Fig.7, the sensitivity of Bessel function to the variation of the truncation factor is shown with the purple line. A parametric analysis should be performed to fully characterized the influence of the function to these parameter. It should be kept in mind that it strongly depends on the training set available. For the present data set, the compromise value of $r_0 = 0.5$ allows to have a higher initial uncertainty. The meta-model uncertainty is in the range of $[1.0 \times 10^{-4}, 1.0 \times 10^{-2}]$ for all the selected r_0 values, oscillating during the evolution and converging with a value of about 1.0×10^{-3} . For this reason, using this kernel the meta-model uncertainty is not effective as stop criterion but still drives the dynamic update. Despite this fact, the convergence has been reached in all cases using a limited number of points, with a residual $E_{RMS} \sim 1.0 \times 10^{-2}$. A different $U(\xi)$ trend is observed using r_0 as stochastic variable, as it can

Figure 6: Gauss Wave Packet behaviour to the stochastic variables $k \sim \text{Unif}[0.0028, 5.2]$, for: $x_0 = 0.5$ (top), $r_0 \sim \text{Unif}[0.01 - 1.0]$ (center) and both r_0 and k on the bottom.

be seen in Fig.8. Here, the values of U are in the order of magnitude 1.0×10^{-2} without varying significantly during the iterations. Although the high number of samples added in the central area, where the function is rather flat, the surrogate model still reports a high uncertainty when converged. For the Bessel kernel, this phenomenon appears mainly when r_0 is used as variable, as it can be noted also where both the parameters are varied (see Fig.9). In the latter case, the uncertainty is related to the variability of the r_0 parameter, being it higher than the one obtained varying only k . It is worth noting that the number of the TS points required for the convergence is lower than the cases with one stochastic variable, and the RMS errors comparable. Here, the variability of both the parameters leads the meta-model to converge with a lower number of points in that area.

Since having r_0 as variable did not provide promising results, a last case has been analysed using only the stochastic variable k . To force the meta-model to provide significant values of uncertainty with Bessel kernel, the upper bound of the stochastic variable has been increased by a factor 10. The results of the meta-model prediction are reported in Fig.10 where it can be seen how the number of samples needed for the convergence is lower than all the other cases analysed so far

Figure 7: Truncated Bessel kernel behaviour to the stochastic variable $k \sim \text{Unif}[0.0028, 5.2]$, for: $x_0 = 0.1$ (top), $x_0 = 0.5$ (center), $x_0 = 1.0$ (bottom).

Figure 8: Truncated Bessel kernel behaviour to the stochastic variable $r_0 \sim \text{Unif}[0.1 - 1.0]$, for $k = 4$.

Figure 9: Truncated Bessel kernel behaviour to the stochastic variables $r_0 \sim \text{Unif}[0.1 - 1.0]$ and $k \sim \text{Unif}[0.0028, 5.2]$.

for the Bessel basis function. In Fig.11 it can be observed (green line) that r_0 doesn't influence the maximum uncertainty range significantly also in this range of k . Finally, in Fig.12 a comparison

Figure 10: Truncated Bessel kernel behaviour to the stochastic variables $k \sim \text{Unif}[0.0028, 52.0]$ for $x_0 = 0.5$.

Figure 11: Maximum uncertainty for the initial training set as a function of r_0 parameter using Bessel kernel with $k \sim \text{Unif}[0.0028, 5.2]$ and $k \sim \text{Unif}[0.0028, 52.0]$.

of the uncertainty evolution is reported for Bessel and polynomial kernels. The irregular trend that all curves exhibit further confirms the necessity of formulating a different strategy as convergence criterion. Fig.13 shows the uncertainty trend for Bessel and polynomial kernels using a tuned value of U_{max} as convergence. For the polynomial case, a lower value of convergence has been imposed

in order to increase the number of iterations, due to the fluctuating behaviour that characterizes its trend. For Bessel a good surrogate model was obtained using a less strict convergence value.

Figure 12: Uncertainty trend as a function of the number of samples added to the TS for Bessel, Polynomial and Cosine wave packet kernels.

Figure 13: Comparison between the uncertainty trend of Polynomial kernel and Bessel kernel with $k \sim \text{Unif}[0.0028, 52.0]$ using the U_{max} as a convergence criterion.

The last kernel analysed is the Cosine wave packet. In Fig.14 the cases with k variable for $r_0 = 0.5$, $r_0 \sim \text{Unif}[0.01, 0.1]$ with $k = 4$, and both stochastic variables are reported. The convergence has been reached for most of the cases analysed but, as it can be observed in the error graphs in Fig.10, the trend is rather irregular with very high spikes of error at certain iterations. The uncertainty trends are shown in Fig.12 (b) in comparison to the best case of Bessel and the polynomial trends. Due to the different order of magnitude of the trends, a logarithmic scale has been used. A wider range of k was also tested for the Cosine wave packet kernel which led to a higher residual uncertainty and more oscillations between the TS points at convergence. For the sake of brevity, these results are not addressed in the paper.

Figure 14: Cosine Wave Packet behaviour to the stochastic variables $k \sim \text{Unif}[0.0028, 5.2]$ for $r_0 = 0.5$ (top), $r_0 \sim \text{Unif}[0.01, 0.1]$ (center) and both (bottom).

5.1 An application case: the shielding factor

In this subsection, the application of the surrogate model adaptive technique using Bessel and Polynomial kernels is used for the application case of noise shielding associated to an airfoil geometry. The acoustic describer herein used for the noise shielding effect characterization is the

Figure 15: The noise shielding of an airfoil geometry with unitary chord in presence of a uniform flow.

Insertion Loss (IL). In the frequency domain, it can be defined as it follows

$$IL = 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{\tilde{p}_I}{\tilde{p}_T} \right) = SPL_I - SPL_T \quad (5)$$

where $\tilde{p}_T = \tilde{p}_I + \tilde{p}_S$ is the total pressure, \tilde{p}_I the incident pressure, \tilde{p}_S the scattered pressure and SPL is the sound pressure level. Pressure data are computed through numerical simulations using a boundary integral formulation to solve the exterior boundary value problem for the convected Helmholtz equation. Specifically, a validated in-house code has been used which implements a zero-th order boundary element method based on the collocation method.

The benchmark consists in a unit point source emitting in an acoustic field in presence of a uniform flow (see Fig.15). The target function is therefore represented by the IL measured at an array of microphones placed $6 - chord$ away from the scatterer. This benchmark has been used to test the RBF adaptive approach with oscillating kernels applied to a $1D$ problem (where the microphones position is the meta-model variable), and a $2D$ problem involving microphones and source position over the airfoil, as design variables.

The first case presented is the $1D$ IL as function of the microphone position. The results for the polynomial and Bessel kernel are shown in Fig.16 and 17. The convergence has been studied up to 1% of UQ error to see how the two kernels evolve. To reach 5% UQ error, the same number of points (33 samples for polynomial and 34 for Bessel) has been added to the meta-model training set, converging to a similar value of RMS error (see Fig.17 (b)). To reach 1% of UQ error, the polynomial surrogate model requires a much higher number of points (544 points) than the Bessel one (119 points). It is worth noting how the trend of the meta-model uncertainty is regularly decreasing for the Bessel kernel from an initial value of $U_{max} = 24.1$ to $U_{max} = 5.4 \times 10^{-2}$ once converged. A similar trend, although at a lesser extent, can be observed for the error evolution. This is a key aspect to consider for the meta-model generation as the uncertainty is the only parameter which drives the process, representing a highly desirable feature. In the $2D$ case, this characteristic is even more prominent as it can be seen in the error and uncertainty plots in Fig.18 (c,d) and 19 (c,d). For this application, Bessel kernel has been used in a global definition imposing a truncation factor $r_0 = 1.0$ in the normalized design variables domain. Bessel presents a smoother uncertainty than the polynomial kernel with higher values at the beginning which quasi-monotonically decrease adding points to the TS. On the other hands, it is well-known that

polynomial RBF in adaptive scheme tends to concentrate samples in areas where the curvature of the function is high due to the dominant values of uncertainty predicted by the kernel, based on the current knowledge (TS points information). For this reason, U_{max} decreases in the overall domain until that local area has been sufficiently inspected, adding TS points to improve the meta-model knowledge. Only when new samples capture a region of the domain not yet explored, the measured uncertainty suddenly increases again. This fact explains why the trend of U_{max} , and consequently the UQ error, fluctuate during the iterations. On the contrary, using Bessel kernel leads to a more uniform distribution of the samples within the design space which justifies the lower number of data necessary to converge. The results obtained for these cases study show that Bessel oscillating kernel better captures the dynamic behaviour of the aeroacoustic phenomenon when compared to standard kernels, such as polynomial splines.

Figure 16: 1D Insertion Loss meta-models at $f = 1600$ Hz. First row are the results obtained using polynomial kernel with stochastic variable $\alpha \sim \text{Unif}[1.0, 3.0]$. Second row are the results obtained with Bessel kernel, varying k parameter in $k \sim \text{Unif}[0.021, 39.0]$ with $r_0 = 1.0$.

Figure 17: On the left, the comparison between the uncertainty trends of Polynomial and Bessel kernels; On the right, the comparison of the UQ errors.

Figure 18: 2D Insertion Loss meta-models at $f = 1600$ Hz using polynomial kernel with stochastic variable $\alpha \sim \text{Unif}[1.0, 3.0]$. Convergence set at 1% UQ error.

(a) bessel, initial TS

(b) bessel, 343 points added

(c) bessel, error trend

(d) bessel, uncertainty trend

Figure 19: 2D Insertion Loss meta-models at $f = 1600$ Hz using Bessel kernel with stochastic variable $k \sim \text{Unif}[0.021, 39.0]$ with $r_0 = 1.0$. Convergence set at 2.5% UQ error.

6 Conclusions

In this paper oscillatory and non-oscillatory kernels have been tested as basis-functions for RBF meta-modelling techniques. In particular they have been applied to an adaptive approach based on statistic quantities. Some of them present compact support, such as the non oscillatory polynomial spline and the Gauss-Laguerre function and the oscillatory Gaussian wave packet. Next to these, oscillatory kernels with compact support (truncated Bessel and Cosine wave packet functions) have been taken into account. All of them have been tested on an aeroacoustic benchmark composed by the pressure generated by an isotropic source moving at a certain speed in a uniform flow. Details about the convergence trends and the evolutions of the model uncertainty, which is quantified by means of the 95% confidence band of the meta-model prediction, are addressed. Although each kernel parameter has been tuned to adequate values, only Bessel presented the suitable characteristics required for the specific application. A 1D and a 2D preliminary aeroacoustic cases study of noise shielding have been presented. Here, the analyses have been carried out using the polynomial kernel as reference case and the Bessel kernel, which have demonstrated to behave qualitatively well. Further studies are envisioned to improve the parameters tuning process for the class of oscillatory kernels, to analyse the influence of the initial training set data and to introduce a regularisation technique for those cases in which the system is ill-conditioned.

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REFERENCES

- [1] M. Buhmann, *Radial basis functions: theory and implementations*, 1st ed. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2003, ch. 7, 14.
- [2] R. Schaback, *A practical guide to radial basis functions*. Electronic Resource, 2007.
- [3] S. Volpi, M. Diez, N. Gaul, H. Song, U. Iemma, K. Choi, E. Campana, and F. Stern, “Development and validation of a dynamic metamodel based on stochastic radial basis functions and uncertainty quantification.” *Structural and Multidisciplinary Optimization*, vol. 51, no. 2, pp. 347, 368, 2015.
- [4] B. Fornberg, E. Larsson, and G. Wright, “A new class of oscillatory radial basis functions.” *Comput. Math. Appl.*, vol. 51, no. 8, pp. 1209, 1222, 2006.
- [5] J. Lin, W. Chen, and S. K.Y., “A new radial basis function for helmholtz problem.” *Engineering Analysis with Boundary Elements*, vol. 36, no. 12, pp. 1923, 1930, 2012.
- [6] M. Londoño and H. Montegranario, “Radial basis function-generated finite differences with bessel weights for the 2d helmholtz equation.” *arXiv Cornell University*, 2019.
- [7] J. Rashidinia and M. Khasi, “Stable gaussian radial basis function method for solving helmholtz equations.” *Computational Methods for Differential Equations*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 138,151, 2019.
- [8] L. Burghignoli, M. Rossetti, F. Centracchio, and U. Iemma, “Noise shielding metamodels based on stochastic radial basis functions,” in *ICSV26*, 2019.
- [9] S. Mousaviraad, W. He, M. Diez, and F. Stern, “Framework for convergence and validation of stochastic uncertainty quantification and relationship to deterministic verification and validation,” *Int. J Uncertainty Quantification*, vol. 3, no. 5, pp. 371, 395, 2013.